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ADULT ADHD: DISCOVERY AND IMPACTS OF DIAGNOSIS AT AGE 40

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ABSTRACT

This study analyzes, through scientific literature, the challenges and possibilities of adults with ADHD. According to Patrícia Mattos (2011), “Untreated ADHD can result in significant challenges in academic and professional life, leading to a cycle of frustration and low self-esteem”. Therefore, diagnosis followed by adequate treatment means progress and personal and professional self-fulfillment.